

The 100 varieties screened could be divided into five response groups (see table). Long-jiang-ao, Radiation 8-1, B-8, and Pioneer 1 were tolerant of butachlor; Long-jiang-dao, B-8, Wu-jie gu, and Er-jiu-nan 1 were tolerant of thiobencarb. IR30, IR54, and Fu-yu 1 were susceptible to both herbicides. □

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Grain quality and nutritional value

Induced variation in aromatic rice cultivars

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Traditional aromatic varieties Karnal Local and Bindli were irradiated with 30 kR gamma rays to obtain semidwarf, nonlodging mutants that retain parental cooking quality characteristics. Only morphological mutants were selected and grown to the M₅ generation.

Important agronomic traits were recorded on five randomly selected plants per mutant. Bulk milled rice samples were used for grain quality analysis.

All short-statured mutants selected from Karnal Local tend to lodge and are near or inferior to the parent in yield per plant (see table). Mutants KLM-14 and KLM-24 possess longer and finer grains with desirable alkali spreading value and amylose content. Except for Karnal Local Mutant-8 (nonaromatic), all mutants have strong aroma.

All mutants selected from Bindli are strongly aromatic. Mutants below 100

cm height have thick, sturdy stems and relatively upright, dark green leaves. Bindli Mutants (BM) 34, 65, and 68 have desirable alkali spreading value and amylose content. BM64 is taller than its parent.

Early-maturing aromatic strains, whether land races or developed through recombination breeding/mutation, that flower and mature at higher temperature and relatively high humidity do not develop aroma or develop only mild aroma. BM21 and BM24, despite having very short durations, maintained strong aroma and parental level of amylose content and alkali spreading value when they flowered and matured in Sep in North India. □

Range and mean for induced variations.

Character	Karnal Local	24 mutants of Karnal Local			Bindli	23 mutants of Bindli		
		Range	Mean ^a	SD		Range	Mean ^a	SD
Plant height (cm)	135.60	76.00-134.40	104.53	15.35	146.40	86.80-172.10	101.04	21.65
Tillers (no./plant)	15.00	10.00- 22.00	15.00	3.18	13.00	6.00- 17.00	12.12	2.60
Yield (g/plant)	29.30	4.50- 29.30	20.17	5.85	20.84	5.62- 37.14	21.19	7.85
Test grain weight ^b (g)	23.00	17.00- 25.80	21.10	2.31	18.00	10.50- 20.00	18.07	2.24
Filled grains (no./panicle)	85.00	20.00-103.00	65.72	20.33	80.00	57.00- 140.00	94.58	20.36
Duration (d)	150.00	132.00-164.00	152.64	10.88	161.00	110.00- 166.00	156.60	15.00
Length (L) of milled rice (mm)	7.55	6.95- 8.88	7.62	0.47	4.77	3.22- 4.80	4.56	0.36
Breadth (B) of milled rice (mm)	1.78	1.40- 2.23	1.82	0.18	2.58	2.20- 2.68	2.52	0.12
L/B ratio	4.24	3.37- 5.80	4.22	0.64	1.85	1.74- 1.92	1.80	0.09
Alkali spreading value	3.00	3.00- 4.00	3.56	0.50	4.00	3.00- 4.00	3.78	0.41
Amylose content (%)	25.5	17.00- 29.50	24.02	4.02	27.00	23.00- 29.00	25.16	1.28

^aIncludes parent. ^bOne thousand randomly selected grains used to compute test grain weight.

Hua-03 — a high-protein indica rice

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Hua-03 is a newly released high-protein, early indica variety with wide

Table 1. Some agronomic characteristics and protein content of Hua-03.^a Wuhan, China, 1983-88.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Protein content (% dry wt brown rice)
Hua-03	113	76.96	568.13	54.20	25.20	7.0	13.72
Guang-Lu-Ai 4	117	63.31	511.21	53.16	25.18	6.2	10.50

^aMean of 5 sites.